

A Study on Emphysematous Pyelonephritis Presenting at a Tertiary Care Hospital in South India

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Abstract:

Background: An uncommon, severe acute necrotizing kidney infection called emphysematous pyelonephritis (EPN) is characterized by the presence of gas in the renal parenchyma, collecting system, and perirenal tissue. Women are more likely than men to get EPN, and people with diabetes are more susceptible to infection. *Escherichia coli* is the most common causative pathogen in nearly 70% of the reported EPN cases. A conservative approach with antibiotics, image-guided drainage, and improved imaging modalities is necessary in the management of EPN.

Methods: We conducted a Retrospective study for a period of 3 years (2023- 2024) in ESICMC, Kalaburgi, Karnataka. We included all the patients diagnosed with Emphysematous Pyelonephritis as the participants of this study. Data on demographic profile, clinical features, and laboratory investigations, imaging studies, management modalities and outcome of patients were recorded retrospectively. Radiological classification was done based on Huang and Tseng.

Results: 21 patients diagnosed with Emphysematous pyelonephritis had a female/male ratio of 4:1 and diabetics were 81%. Fever (86%) was the commonest symptom followed by dysuria & frequency (52%) and flank pain (48%). Renal angle tenderness (71%) was the commonest sign. Among the biochemical abnormalities, we found acute renal dysfunction as 38%, hyperglycemia as 81%, leukocytosis as 71%, and dyselectrolytemia as 43% and thrombocytopenia as 19%. 8 patients (38%) were treated under medical management with antibiotics alone, 8 patients (38%) were treated both medically and with a DJ stent. 2 of them were treated both medically and with ultrasound guided Percutaneous drainage (PCD). 1 patient underwent Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy (PCNL) and 2 patients underwent Nephrectomy.

Conclusion: Hence, we conclude that, radiographic diagnosis of emphysematous pyelonephritis is necessary. We recommend for early aggressive medical treatment with Percutaneous Drainage (PCD) and DJ stent and suggest that Nephrectomy should be considered only if patients deteriorate or do not improve on conservative treatment.

Keywords: Emphysematous pyelonephritis, antibiotics, PCD, PCNL, Nephrectomy.

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Introduction

Emphysematous pyelonephritis (EPN) is an acute severe necrotizing infection of the renal parenchyma and its surrounding tissues that results in the presence of gas in the renal parenchyma, collecting system, or perinephric tissue. Pathogenic bacteria that produce mixed acid fermentation in an environment of hyperglycemia within ischemic tissues are the cause of gas production in EPN. This causes tissue to be destroyed, promotes purulent infection, and inhibits the expulsion of gas produced locally. [1-4] Although Schultz and Klorfein (1962) [5] coined the term "emphysematous pyelonephritis," Kelly and

MacCallum (1898) [6] described the first case of EPN. Gas-forming bacteria, high tissue glucose levels (which encourage rapid bacterial growth), impaired tissue perfusion (diabetic nephropathy can lead to additional compromise of regional oxygen delivery in the kidney, which results in tissue ischemia and necrosis, as well as nitrogen released during tissue necrosis), and impaired vascular supply have all been linked to the pathophysiology of EPN. [4] Finally, impaired tissue perfusion has been linked to a defective immune response. While individuals with diabetes may have an environment that is conducive to the growth of gas-producing

bacteria when their tissue glucose level is high, hyperglycemia causes renal vasculopathy, renal neuropathy, and leukocyte dysfunction. [7]

Women are more likely than men to get EPN, and people with diabetes are more susceptible to infection. Renal stone disease, urinary tract anatomical abnormalities, and immunodeficiency are prevalent comorbidities among the non-diabetic population. [8] *Escherichia coli* is the most common causative pathogen with the organism isolated on urine or pus cultures in nearly 70% of the reported EPN cases followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (29%). [7]

Wan and Rullard [9] found that elevated urine red blood cell counts, azotemia, and thrombocytopenia are indicators of poor prognosis in EPN. The degree of necrosis brought on by the infectious process and the existence of renal vein thrombosis is likely reflected in the severity of hematuria in EPN patients. A poor prognosis has also been linked to altered consciousness, hypotension, severe proteinuria, and infection extension to the perinephric region. [10]

Nephrectomy was the typical treatment until the mid-1980s since attempts to preserve the kidney surgically resulted in mortality ranging from 60% to 80%. Nonetheless, the mortality rate for patients with EPN has dropped to 25% (1%–46%) in recent years. [11] An initial conservative approach is sense, especially with the availability of powerful antibiotics, image-guided drainage, and improved imaging modalities. [12] Chen et al. (1996) [13] demonstrated that a viable substitute for nephrectomy was antibiotic therapy in conjunction with computed tomography-guided percutaneous catheter drainage (PCD).

So, a retrospective study was planned in our institute to study the outcome of management of patients with emphysematous pyelonephritis.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this research was to study the outcome of management of patients with emphysematous pyelonephritis at our institute.

Methodology

We conducted a retrospective study for a period of 3 years (2023- 2024) in ESICMC, Kalaburgi, Karnataka. We included all the patients diagnosed with Emphysematous Pyelonephritis as the participants of this study during the 3 years period. All the 21 patients diagnosed with EPN included in this study were managed in ESICMC KALABURGI. Data on demographic profile, clinical features, laboratory investigations, imaging studies, outcome of patients were recorded retrospectively. The baseline characteristics such as age, sex, comorbidity status and status of glucose control were included.

The clinical features included symptoms at presentation, duration of symptoms and physical findings like mental status, hemodynamic status, palpable mass or tenderness, temperature. The laboratory variables were serum creatinine level, total leukocyte count, platelet count, coagulation profile, serum electrolytes and Random Blood Sugar (RBS) levels.

After admission, all the patients were initially managed by correction and maintenance of fluid and hemodynamic status, aggressive sugar control, optimization of coagulation value and antibiotics.

Initially broad-spectrum antibiotics such as Ceftriaxone and Sulbactam or Piperacillin and Tazobactam were used as first line antibiotics. Aminoglycosides were added to patients with normal renal function tests. Antibiotics were changed in accordance with the culture sensitivity reports when it was available.

Percutaneous drainage (PCD) of the renal or extrarenal lesion was done using ultrasonographic guidance. Double J (DJ) stent was placed for patients with obstructive causes. Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy (PCNL) was done in patients with renal calculi. At the time of discharge, patients were put on either levofloxacin or oral cephalosporins for four weeks. PCD was removed on an inpatient basis. DJ was removed after 4 – 6 weeks on outpatient basis.

Huang and Tseng Emphysematous Pyelonephritis CT classification was used in this study, which is categorized as follows,

Huang and Tseng Emphysematous Pyelonephritis CT classification¹⁴

- **Class 1:** Gas in collecting system only.
- **Class 2:** Parenchyma gas only.
- **Class 3A:** Extension of gas into perinephric space.
- **Class 3B:** Extension of gas into pararenal space.
- **Class 4:** EPN in solitary kidney, or bilateral disease.

Statistical Analysis

The data was collected and compiled in MS Excel. Descriptive statistics has been used to present the data. To analyse the data SPSS (Version 26.0) was used. Qualitative variables were expressed as frequency and percentages and Quantitative variables were expressed in Means.

Results

There was a total of 21 patients diagnosed with Emphysematous pyelonephritis and managed in our institute during the above mentioned period for 3 years.

Among the 21 patients, 17 (81%) of them were females and only 4 (19%) were males. The mean age group was in between 35 to 60 years of age.

The comorbid status was analyzed, where 17 (81%) of them were diabetic and 4 patients had ureteric calculi (19%). The clinical presentation as shown in Table 1, represented fever (86%) as the most com-

monest symptom followed by dysuria and frequency (52%), flank pain (48%) and nausea & vomiting (24%) among the EPN patients.

Renal angle tenderness (71%) was the most typical sign found followed by abdominal tenderness (33%), hypotension (24%) and altered mental status (14%).

Table 1: Clinical Presentation of Patients with Emphysematous Pyelonephritis (N=21)

Symptoms	No Of Patients (%)	Signs	No Of Patients (%)
Fever	18 (86%)	Renal angle tenderness	15 (71%)
Dysuria & frequency	11 (52%)	Abdominal tenderness	7 (33%)
Flank pain	10 (48%)	Hypotension	5 (24%)
Nausea & vomiting	5 (24%)	Altered mental status	3 (14%)

Table 2: Biochemical Abnormalities of Patients with Emphysematous Pyelonephritis at Presentation (N=21)

Biochemical Abnormality	No Of Patients (%)
Hyperglycemia	17 (81%)
Leukocytosis	15 (71%)
Dyselectrolytemia	9 (43%)
Raised serum creatinine	8 (38%)
Altered coagulation profile	5 (24%)
Thrombocytopenia	4 (19%)

Biochemical tests were conducted for all the patients as depicted in Table 2. Hyperglycemia was found among 17 (81%) patients.

Also, biochemical abnormalities like leukocytosis (71%) were quite common along with other abnormalities as dyselectrolytemia (43%), raised serum creatinine (38%), altered coagulation profile (24%) and thrombocytopenia (19%). CT Abdomen

was taken for the patients and Radiological classification was done among the patients based on Huang and Tseng. [10]

Majority of them (48%) belonged to Class 1. 28% and 19% were classified under Class 2 and Class 3A respectively. Only 1 patient belonged to Class 4. However, there was none classified under Class 3B [Figure 1,2].

Figure 1: Radiological Classification of Patients with Emphysematous Pyelonephritis (n=21)

Figure 2: Ct Abdomen of a Patient with Emphysematous Pyelonephritis

All the 21 patients admitted in our institute were managed in different modalities. 8 patients (38%) were treated under medical management with antibiotics and another 8 patients (38%) were under both medical management and DJ stent. 2 of them (9.5%) were treated both medically and with ultra-

sound guided Percutaneous drainage (PCD). 1 patient (5%) underwent Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy (PCNL). As 2 patients did not respond to conservative therapy, they underwent Nephrectomy (9.5%), where one of them died during the course of treatment [Figure 3].

Figure 3: Management Modalities of Patients with Emphysematous Pyelonephritis (n=21)

Discussion

A uncommon, severe acute necrotizing kidney infection called emphysematous pyelonephritis is characterized by the presence of gas in the renal parenchyma, collecting system, and perirenal tissue. [14] Studies by Wan et al [9] and Lu et al [15] depicted that women are more likely to get EPN than men, which was similar in our study where 81% affected were females with a female/male ratio of 4:1 respectively. This was like a study by Wan et al, [9] where they found a female/male ratio

of 3:1. Lu et al. [15] revealed a pronounced female domination in their study, with a ratio of 12:1. People with diabetes are more susceptible to infection where our study had a diabetic prevalence of 81%. In diabetic patients, elevated glucose levels may create an ideal environment for the growth of bacteria that produce gas.

Among the population that is diabetic, or with renal stone disease, urinary tract abnormalities, and immunosuppression are frequently linked morbidities. [7,8,16] Since there is vascular impairment in the

pyelonephritic kidney, rapid catabolism and bacterial infection have been proposed as the causes of increased gas production. Gas is produced by gram-negative facultative anaerobic microbes like *E. Coli* through the fermentation of glucose and lactate. A significant amount of carbon dioxide is produced as a result of this process. The most frequent bacterium linked to EPN is *E. Coli*; *Proteus* and *Klebsiella* are also involved. [7,10,16]

According to Khaira A et al, Narlawar RS et al and Roy C et al, the physical manifestations, including dysuria, fever and rigors, nausea, vomiting and flank pain are indicative of pyelonephritis. [17-19] In our study fever (86%), dysuria (52%) and flank pain (48%) were the most common presenting symptoms and renal angle tenderness (71%) was the most commonest sign, whereas fever (100%) and flank pain (50%) were the most common symptoms and renal angle tenderness (83%) as the most commonest sign detected in a study by Khandelwal AK. [16] Acute renal dysfunction (33%), hyperglycemia (83%), thrombocytopenia (16%), acid-base abnormalities on blood gas analysis (33%), and impaired consciousness are among the clinical symptoms found by Khandelwal AK. [16] Huang and Tseng interpreted that the initial presentation was thrombocytopenia (46%), acute renal functional impairment (35%), disturbance in consciousness (19%), or shock (29%). [10] Similar to Khandelwal AK, we found hyperglycemia as 81%, acute renal dysfunction as 38%, leukocytosis as 71%, thrombocytopenia as 19%, acid-base abnormalities on blood gas analysis as 43% among patients in our study.

Studies done by Huang & Tseng, Wan YL et al and Tang HJ et al shows radiographic diagnosis of emphysematous pyelonephritis is necessary because most clinical and laboratory results only show sepsis with a renal etiology. While an abdominal X-ray can raise suspicions due to an anomalous gas shadow in the renal region, a CT scan or ultrasonography can confirm the presence of intrarenal gas and corroborate the EPN diagnosis.

Because CT is more sensitive and can reveal characteristics of parenchymal damage, it is favored for defining the extent of EPN. Abdominal CT is therefore required for an early diagnosis and ongoing EPN therapy. [10,14,20] We used CT scans in our study and classified patients with EPN based on Huang and Tseng. The classification by Huang and Tseng is superior due to the better prognostic value and is also helpful in selecting a management protocol. Most of the patients (48%) belonged to Class 1 followed by 28% and 19% under Class 2 and Class 3A respectively. Only 1 patient belonged to Class 4. However, there was none classified under Class 3B in our study. A study by Falagas ME et al [10] says that along with proper glycemic control, basic resuscitation techniques include oxygen, in-

travenous fluids, acid-base balance correction, and the necessary antibiotic should be initiated. Since gram-negative bacteria are still the most frequent causing agents, they should be the focus of the first antibiotic treatment. Our study included all the above measures in treating our patients.

As per Ubee SS et al, [7] the local hospital policy should direct the use of cephalosporins, quinolones, aminoglycosides, and β lactamase inhibitors. The kind and quantity of organisms as well as each one's unique sensitivity can all be taken into consideration while selecting antibiotics. In this study, we treated 8 patients (38%) with medical management by using antibiotics alone, which was similar to the study by Khandelwal AK [16] where 6 of their patients (50%) were treated with antibiotic therapy alone. Another 8 patients (38%) in the present study were treated with medical management and underwent DJ stent. This was less when compared to studies done by Joshi et al [21] and M Eswarappa et al, [22] where 8 patients (100%) and 27 patients (53%) respectively underwent DJ stenting either alone or in combination with PCD or Nephrectomy. One therapy option for EPN is percutaneous drainage (PCD), which was initially demonstrated by Hudson et al in 1986. [21] Further case studies done by Khaira A et al [17] and Narlawar RS et al [18] have demonstrated that patients can effectively get PCD treatment when it is utilized in conjunction with medical therapy, leading to a notable decrease in fatality rates. In almost 70% of cases, PCD aids in maintaining the damaged kidney's function. Patients with confined gas pockets and those who exhibit functional renal tissue should undergo PCD. [16] Similarly, we had treated 2 patients with PCD in combination with medical management using antibiotics.

In our study, Nephrectomy was done only in 2 patients (9.5%) as they did not respond to conservative therapy, where one of them did not survive post nephrectomy. As per Dhabalia et al, [23] a nephrectomy should be considered for a limited number of individuals with renal parenchymal deterioration, Class 3A or Class 3B gas distribution, the simultaneous presence of two or more risk factors, or non-functioning kidneys.

Conclusion

In this series of patients with EPN, majority had Diabetes Mellitus, most of them were women, and *E. coli* was the most frequently isolated pathogen. Hence we conclude that, radiographic diagnosis of emphysematous pyelonephritis is necessary. We recommend early aggressive medical treatment with Percutaneous Drainage (PCD) and DJ stent and suggest that Nephrectomy should be considered only if patients deteriorate or do not improve on conservative treatment.

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